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Employable Skills for Hospitality Graduates as Perceived Among Hotel Supervisors in Cebu City

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Abstract

Hospitality is one of the most significant components of the tourism industry. Graduates of hospitality management in the twenty-first century are facing an increasingly competitive and unstable employment market; thus, it is critical that they should be equipped with skills that enable them to maximize their full potential. According to McNair (2003), in the future, graduates will need to have greater ownership of their employable skills as well as the confidence to cope with economic upheavals in order to capitalize on career opportunities. Employable skills are those that prepare students specifically for the world of work. In common terms, they cover a range of competencies within the categories of hospitality operations skills, human resource skills, personal skills, and conceptual skills. This study relates to employers perceived of Hotel and Restaurant Management graduate skills as deemed required by need for accelerated performance levels in hospitality the businesses for fast change in the skills required of university graduates and to understand what industry needs from education and have education is accomplishing its objectives to prepare qualified graduate for the changing hospitality industry in the Philippines and it aims to determine the factor that measures the employable skills of the hotel. In the context of the findings of the study, the author concluded that the most employable skills as perceived among hotel supervisors in three departments, namely: Housekeeping Department, Front Office Department, and Food and Beverage Department were Front Office Operational Ability, Leadership skills, Communication skills, Cooperative team building, Critical thinking ability, Hands-on experience, and Strategic planning were the seven employable skills possessing a most or significant need for hotel supervisors. However, Restaurant Operational Management, Handling difficult people, Problem-solving and identification and interrelationship possess moderately crucial than their ability to perform the skills while Lodging Administration, Negotiating Skills, Computer Application and Finance and Accounting. Interestingly all four of the lowest rated employable skills in the hospitality industry are cornerstones taught, and it should still be retained because of its essential ratings among hotel supervisors.

Keywords: Employable skills, Tourism, Hospitality Industry

1. Introduction

1.1 Rationale of the Study

In this context, hospitality management education may have a uniquely valuable role to play. A recent survey by the Hotel, Restaurant, and Resort Association of Cebu (HRRAC) revealed that employers recruiting graduates placed an unusually high value on Human Resource Skills (i.e. leadership skills, communication skills, Cooperative team building, negotiating skills, harmonious guest relations, handling difficult people, employee relations and public relations skills. In new workplace skills such as People skills that include critical thinking ability skills, problem- solving and identification skills, decision-making skills, computer application skills, multilingual skills, research skills, professionalism, and hands-on experience. The majority of employers in the study valued analytical thinking and problem-solving skills just as much, if not more so than subject knowledge. The generation of new ideas help drive innovation within the organization, a sense of maturity and the demonstration of leadership were also high on the list of employable skills sought out by employers.

On the other hand tourism industry is not just about the facilities and attractions provided for visitors. It is about people and especially about the relationship between the customer and the individual providing service. Everybody employed in the tourism industry needs to have the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values to provide the standard of product and services that a customer expect. Knowing about the tourism industry, it's component parts and especially where you fit in is an important starting point to a successful career in tourism.

According to (Sommerville, 2007), the hospitality industry is a people industry. But for once let us not focus on the people who are our guest and customers but on those people who are serving our guests and customers, those who work in the hospitality operation are the company's most valuable asset, more valuable than the equipment. When management takes care of its employees, the employees will certainly be more motivated to take care of the guest and customers.

Our workforces are our greatest strength and our competitive advantage. The involvement of an employee is one of the elements of the success of the hospitality industry. The responsibilities of hotel supervisors in the hospitality industry are continuously changing. Obtaining and keeping a management job in a Food and Beverage Department, Housekeeping Department and Front Office Department or hotel require that a person have the ability to change. Successful managers have the enthusiasm to respond to the changing needs and challenges of their organization (Woods & King, 2002). Some of these challenges are due to the changes affecting the hospitality industry today. Consequently, the curriculum and the methods used to prepare entry-level managers in this field should also be designed to fit the demands of today's industry.

1.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is premised on Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory. Bandura (1986) advanced a view of human functioning that accords a central role to cognitive, vicarious, self-regulatory, and self-reflective processes in human adaptation and change. People are viewed as self-organizing, proactive, self-reflecting, and self-regulating rather than as reactive organisms shaped and shepherded by environmental forces or driven by concealed inner impulses. From this theoretical perspective, human functioning is viewed as the product of a dynamic interplay of personal, behavioral, and environmental influences. For example, how people interpret the results of their own behavior informs and alters their environments and the personal factors they possess which, in turn, inform and alter subsequent behavior. This is the foundation of Bandura's (1986) conception of *reciprocal determinism*, the view that (a) personal factors in the form of cognition, affect, and biological events, (b) behavior, and (c) environmental influences create interactions that result in *triadic reciprocity*. Bandura altered the label of his theory from social learning to social "cognitive" both to distance it from prevalent social learning theories of the day and to emphasize that cognition plays a critical role in people's capability to construct reality, self-regulate, encode information, and perform behaviors.

The reciprocal nature of the determinants of human functioning in social cognitive theory makes it possible for therapeutic and counseling efforts to be directed at personal, environmental, or behavioral factors. Strategies for increasing well-being can be aimed at improving emotional, cognitive, or motivational processes, increasing behavioral competencies, or altering the social conditions under which people live and work. In school, for example, teachers have the challenge of improving the academic learning and confidence of the students in their charge. Using social cognitive theory as a framework, teachers can work to improve their students' emotional states and to correct their faulty self-beliefs and habits of thinking (personal factors), improve their academic skills and self-regulatory practices (behavior), and alter the school and classroom structures that may work to undermine student success (environmental factors).

Social cognitive theory is rooted in the view of human agency in which individuals are agents proactively engaged in their own development and can make things happen by their actions. Key to this sense of agency is the fact that, among other personal factors, individuals possess self-beliefs that enable them to exercise a measure of control over their thoughts, feelings, and actions, that "what people think, believe, and feel affects how they behave" (Bandura, 1986). Bandura provided a view of human behavior in which the beliefs that people have about themselves are critical elements in the exercise of control and personal agency. Thus, individuals are viewed both as products and as producers of their own environments and of their social systems. Because human lives are not lived in isolation, Bandura expanded the conception of human agency to include collective agency. People work together on shared beliefs about their capabilities and common aspirations to better their lives. This conceptual extension makes the theory applicable to human adaptation and change in collectivistic ally-oriented societies as well as individualistically-oriented ones.

Environments and social systems influence human behavior through psychological mechanisms of the self-system. Hence, the social cognitive theory posits that factors such as economic conditions, socioeconomic status, and educational and familial structures do not affect human behavior directly. Instead, they affect it to the degree that they influence people's aspirations, self-efficacy beliefs, personal standards, emotional states, and other self-regulatory influences. In all, this social cognitive view of human and collective functioning, which marked a departure from the prevalent behaviorist and learning theories of the day, was to have a profound influence on psychological thinking and theorizing during the last two decades of the twentieth century and into the new millennium.

1.3 Objective of the study

This study relates to employers perceived of graduate skills as deemed required by need for accelerated performance levels in hospitality businesses for rapid change in the skills required of university graduates and to understand what industry needs from education and have education is accomplishing its objectives to prepare qualified graduate for the changing hospitality industry in the Philippines and it aims to determine the factor that measures the employable skills of the hotel supervisors.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Research Design

This study made use of the descriptive method using the survey method. The descriptive study is deemed to be appropriate for this research paper since it will seek and collect information without changing anything from the environment. This particular descriptive study will involve one - time interaction with a group of people through the use of the survey method aided by the questionnaire and in this case the hotel supervisors in **Cebu City** to collect the necessary data or information relative to the main variable for this study. According to (Rog. 1998) the descriptive studies can answer the question such as "what is" or "what was" hence the appropriateness of the aforementioned method.

2.2 Research Site

This study has been conducted in Selected Hotel in Cebu City, Philippines.

2.3 Participants

This study made use of the convenient purposive - sampling technique. The purposive sampling is the most appropriate method in determining the respondent for this research since it will make use of the researchers' knowledge that will be used in order to explain the phenomenon under investigation, Hence only the hotel supervisors in Cebu City will be considered for this study. Convenient is non-probability techniques since the researcher will make use of any subject as long as they are hotel supervisors in Cebu City in accordance with their availability and accessibility for this study. Table 1 shows the respondent, hotel name, department, and position.

2.4 Instruments

The study made use of a validated instrument to measure the employable skills in the hotel industry as per the assessment made by the hotel supervisors. The said instrument is made up of two parts: the demographic profile such as age, gender, civil status, work position, highest educational attainment and number of years working in the current position, is contained in Part 1 while the required employable skills has four dimensions such as hospitality operations, human resource skills, personal skills, and conceptual skills is contained in part 2.

2.4 Data Collection and Analysis

2.4.1 Phase I. Initial

The researcher wrote a letter to the Human Resource Department of the selected hotels in Cebu City to ask permission to conduct research. When approval is given, the researcher will approach the different department of the hotels and distribute the instrument to them.

2.4.2 Phase II. Actual gathering

The second phase was given to the respondents three days to answer the questionnaire and provide them with the mobile number in case any classification to the study can be made by them.

2.4.3 Phase III. Post gathering

The researcher went back to the hotels in Cebu City and retrieved the instrument from the respondents. When the retrieval of data is done, the appropriate statistical treatment will be conducted so that prospect inferences on the correlation will be established. In treating the data, composite mean was used in the study.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Required competencies as perceived by the Supervisors in the Hotel Industry.

3.1.1. *On the employable skills in the hotel industry, as perceived by the respondents in Food and Beverage Department, the researcher wanted to find out the employable skills in the context of Hospitality Operations skills working in the hospitality industry.*

Table 1 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in Food and Beverage Department, the researcher wanted to find out the employable skills in the context of Hospitality Operations skills working in the hospitality industry.

SKILLS	1	2	3	4	N	WM	DV	R
A. Hospitality Operations								
1. Lodging Administration	0	3	8	8	19	3.26	GI	7
2. Restaurant Operational Management	0	0	6	13	19	3.68	GI	1
3. Food and Beverage Management	0	1	6	12	19	3.58	GI	2
4. Hospitality Facility Planning and Development	0	1	7	11	19	3.53	GI	3
5. Hospitality Finance and Accounting	0	3	7	9	19	3.32	GI	6
6. Marketing in Hospitality Industry	0	3	6	10	19	3.37	GI	5
7. Front Office Operational Ability	0	1	8	10	19	3.47	GI	4
Composite Mean						3.46	GI	

Table 1 shows that the most employable skills in Food and Beverage Management as perceived by the hotel respondents in Hospitality Operations Skills with the composite mean of 3.46 with an interpretation of hugely important. Restaurant operational management was generated a weighted mean of 3.68 with an interpretation of greatly important; Food and Beverage Management reached a weighted mean of 3.58 with an interpretation of exceedingly important; Hospitality Planning and Development was garnered a weighted mean of 3.53 with an interpretation of much important. The finding shows that Restaurant Operations can be classified as the back of the house operations; working behind the scenes of the establishment or front of the house is in direct contact with customers, either face to face or over the telephone. Restaurant Operations Skills has a vital role to play in delivering products and services. In order for any establishment to be successful, each of the section needs to work together towards a common goal. Restaurant Operations offer foods and drinks to customers, and this department is often divided into smaller units such as bar, restaurants, room service and banquet and function catering.

Legend:

1:00 – 1.74	NI	Not important
1.75 – 2.49	SI	Slightly important
2.50 – 3.24	MI	Moderately Important
3.25 – 4.00	GI	Greatly Important

3.1.2 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in Food and Beverage Department the researcher wanted to find out the employable skills of respondents in the context of Human Resource Skills working in the hospitality industry.

Table 2 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in Food and Beverage Department the researcher wanted to find out the employable skills of respondents in the context of Human Resource Skills working in the hospitality industry.

SKILLS	1	2	3	4	N	WM	DV	R
B. Human Resource Skills								
1. Leadership Skills	0	0	6	13	19	3.68	GI	2
2. Communication Skills	0	0	6	13	19	3.68	GI	2
3. Cooperative Team Building	0	1	4	14	19	3.68	GI	2
4. Negotiating Skills	0	2	9	8	19	3.32	GI	8
5. Harmonious Guests Relations	0	3	5	11	19	3.42	GI	5.5
6. Handling Difficult People	0	2	6	11	19	3.47	GI	4
7. Employee Relations	0	3	6	10	19	3.37	GI	7
8. Public Relations Skills	0	2	7	10	19	3.42	GI	5.5
Composite Mean						3.51	GI	

Table 2 shows that the most employable skills as perceived by the respondents under Human Resource Skills in the hospitality industry with the composite mean of 3.51 with an interpretation of exceedingly important; leadership skills, communication skills, and cooperative team building skills were generated a weighted mean of 3.68 with an interpretation of much important. The finding shows that leadership skills, communications, and cooperative team building were needed to negotiate and provide service to clients while communication skills are associated with listening, presenting, verbalizing and non - verbal communication therefore, the food and beverage department were responsible for tasks such as preparing for service, greeting and seating customers, promoting food and beverage sales, taking orders, serving food and drinks, collecting guest payment of accounts and maintaining service areas while for food production is responsible for the cooking and presentation of food for guests. Tasks may include ordering bulk food, cooking, and presenting the menu items, budgeting, operations of all kitchen equipment, and maintaining of the marketplace for customers taste and food trends.

3.1.3. *On the employable skills in the hotel industry, as perceived by the respondents in the Food and Beverage Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Personal Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.*

Table 3 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in the Food and Beverage Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Personal Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

SKILLS	1	2	3	4	N	WM	DV	R
C. Personal Skills								
1. Critical Thinking Ability	0	2	5	12	19	3.53	GI	3
2. Problem Solving and Identification	0	2	3	14	19	3.63	GI	1.5
3. Decision Making Skills	0	1	9	9	19	3.42	GI	4
4. Computer Application	0	3	14	2	19	2.95	MI	7.5
5. Multilingual Skills/Need of second language	0	5	10	4	19	2.95	MI	7.5
6. Research Skills	0	5	8	6	19	3.05	MI	6
7. Professionalism	0	2	8	9	19	3.37	GI	5
8. Hands on Experience	0	1	5	13	19	3.63	GI	1.5
Composite Mean						3.32	GI	

Table 3 shows that the most employable skill as perceived by the respondents under Personal Skills with the composite mean of 3.32 with an interpretation of greatly important. Problem-solving and identification and hand – on experience culled a weighted mean of 3.63 with an interpretation of greatly important; Critical thinking ability was generated weighted mean of 3.53 with an interpretation of greatly important; Research skills were obtained a weighted mean of 3.07 with an interpretation of moderately important; Computer application skills and

Multilingual skills were procured a weighted mean 2.95 with an interpretation of moderately important. The finding shows that Hospitality establishment is closely interrelated and need to work together to achieve their common goals without the cooperation there would be little or no success. Personal attributes and work ethics of employees within the hospitality industry are important and different roles in the hospitality emphasize different sets of skills. Personal attributes required by all hospitality staff like the attention to detail or work performance, integrity/work ethics/ethical behavior, awareness of confidential issues, and work.

3.1.4. On the employable skills in the hotel industry, as perceived by the respondents in the Food and Beverage Department, the researcher wanted to find out the conceptual skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry

Table 4. On the employable skills in the hotel industry, as perceived by the respondents in the Food and Beverage Department, the researcher wanted to find out the conceptual skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

SKILLS	1	2	3	4	N	WM	DV	R
D. Conceptual Skills								
1. Organizational Structure and Policies	0	2	10	7	19	3.26	GI	3.5
2. Hospitality Laws and Regulations	0	5	7	7	19	3.11	MI	5
3. Principles of Marketing	0	4	13	2	19	2.89	MI	7
4. Finance and Accounting	0	4	10	5	19	3.05	MI	6
5. Human Resource Management	0	2	10	7	19	3.26	GI	3.5
6. Interrelationships	0	0	13	6	19	3.32	GI	2
7. Strategic Planning	0	0	12	7	19	3.37	GI	1
Composite Mean						3.18	MI	

Table 4 shows that the most employable skills as previewed by the respondents in the Conceptual Skills with the composite mean of 3.37 with an interpretation of moderately important. Strategic planning was captured a weighted mean of 3.37 with an interpretation of greatly important; Interrelationships skills acquired a weighted mean of 3.32 with an interpretation of greatly important. While organization structure and policies and human resource management skills were garnered a weighted mean of 3.26 with an interpretation of greatly important. The findings show that strategic plannings are the planning and visioning skills needed by supervisors. Therefore the hospitality industry offers a variety of job opportunities and career pathways. Career moves in the hospitality industry can be horizontal as well as vertical.

On tables, 5 to table 8 revealed the most employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in the Front Office Department.

3.2.5 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in the Front Office Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Hospitality Operations of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

Table 5. On the employable skills in the hotel industry, as perceived by the respondents in the Front Office Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Hospitality Operations of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

SKILLS	1	2	3	4	N	WM	DV	R
A. Hospitality Operations								
1. Lodging Administration	0	3	6	12	21	3.43	GI	6
2. Restaurant Operational Management	0	1	8	12	21	3.52	GI	4
3. Food and Beverage Management	0	2	5	14	21	3.57	GI	2
4. Hospitality Facility Planning and Development	0	2	6	13	21	3.52	GI	4
5. Hospitality Finance and Accounting	0	2	9	10	21	3.38	GI	7
6. Marketing in Hospitality Industry	0	1	8	12	21	3.52	GI	4
7. Front Office Operational Ability	0	1	3	17	21	3.76	GI	1
Composite Mean						3.53	GI	

Table 5 shows that the most employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents Hospitality Operations was generated a composite mean of 3.53 with an interpretation of greatly important; Front office operational ability was reached a weighted mean of 3.76 with an interpretation of greatly important; Food and beverage management was generated a weighted mean of 3.57 with an interpretation of greatly important. While Restaurant Operational Management and Marketing in the Hospitality Industry were procured a weighted mean of 3.52 with an interpretation of greatly important, the finding shows that if you were assigned in the front office department, the staff should know basic knowledge, skills and the standard operating procedure in the hospitality operations.

3.1.6. On the employable skills in the hotel industry, as perceived by the respondents in the Front Office Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Human Resource Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

Table 6. On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in the Front Office Department the researcher wanted to find out the Human Resource Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry

SKILLS	1	2	3	4	N	WM	DV	R
B. Human Resource Skills								
1. Leadership skills	0	0	4	17	21	3.81	GI	3.5
2. Communication skills	0	1	3	17	21	3.76	GI	6
3. Cooperative team building	0	1	2	18	21	3.81	GI	3.5
4. Negotiating skills	0	0	4	17	21	3.81	GI	3.5
5. Harmonious guest relations	0	0	4	17	21	3.81	GI	3.5
6. Handling difficult people	0	0	3	18	21	3.86	GI	1
7. Employee relations	0	1	7	13	21	3.57	GI	8
8. Public Relations skills	0	1	4	16	21	3.71	GI	7
Composite Mean						3.77	GI	

Table 6 shows that the most employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in Human Resource Skills were incurred a composite mean of 3.77 with an interpretation of greatly important. Handling difficult people was generated a weighted mean of 3.86 with an interpretation of greatly important; while leadership skills, cooperative team building; negotiating skills and harmonious guest relations were copped a weighted mean of 3.81 with an interpretation of greatly important. The finding shows that the Front Office is involved in the operation of the accommodation services as well as the reservations and reception areas. Staff in this department is involved in talking and recording and delivering quality products and services to the guests, so inner work standards equated to having high standards of work performance to satisfy the guest needs and expectation and are able to manage a group of difficult people or interact in a one – on – one format.

3.1.7. On the employable skills in the hotel industry, as perceived by the respondents in the Front Office Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Personal Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

Table 7. On the employable skills in the hotel industry, as perceived by the respondents in the Front Office Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Personal Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

SKILLS	1	2	3	4	N	WM	DV	R
C. Personal Skills								
1. Critical thinking Ability	0	0	1	20	21	3.95	GI	1
2. Problem Solving and identification	0	0	3	18	21	3.86	GI	3.5
3. Decision making skills	0	1	0	20	21	3.90	GI	2
4. Computer application	0	1	9	11	21	3.48	GI	6
5. Multilingual skills/need second language	0	3	9	9	21	3.29	GI	8
6. Research skills	0	1	10	10	21	3.43	GI	7
7. Professionalism	0	0	4	17	21	3.81	GI	5
8. Hands – on experience	0	1	1	19	21	3.86	GI	3.5
Composite Mean						3.70	GI	

Table 7 shows that the most employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in Personal skills with the composite mean of 3.70 with the interpretation of greatly important. Critical thinking ability was garnered a weighted mean of 3.95 with an interpretation of greatly important; Decision-Making skills was generated a weighted mean of 3.90 with the interpretation of greatly important; while problem-solving and identification skills were obtained a weighted mean of 3.86 with an interpretation as greatly important. The finding shows that if you were assigned to the front office department, the staff should be careful in judging about the good and bad hotel operations.

3.1.8. On the employable skills in the hotel industry, as perceived by the respondents in the Front Office Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Conceptual Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

Table 8 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in the Front Office Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Conceptual Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

SKILLS	1	2	3	4	N	WM	DV	R
D. Conceptual Skills								
1. Organizational Structure and policies	0	1	8	12	21	3.52	GI	4
2. Hospitality law and regulations	0	1	5	15	21	3.67	GI	1
3. Principle of marketing	0	1	9	11	21	3.48	GI	5
4. Finance and Accounting	0	2	10	9	21	3.33	GI	7
5. Human Resource Management	0	1	10	10	21	3.43	GI	6
6. Interrelationships	0	2	5	14	21	3.57	GI	3
7. Strategic Planning	0	2	4	15	21	3.62	GI	2
Composite Mean						3.52	GI	

Table 8 shows that the most employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in the Conceptual skills with a composite mean of 3.42 with an interpretation as greatly important. Hospitality Law and Regulations has generated a weighted mean of 3.67 with an interpretation as greatly important; Strategic Planning was garnered a weighted mean of 3.62 with an interpretation as greatly important; Interrelationships was secured a weighted mean of 3.57 with an interpretation as greatly important. The finding shows that if you were in the front office, the staff should know the basic knowledge about laws and regulation in order to know the dos and don'ts of the hospitality operations in terms of policies and procedures.

On tables, 9 to table 11 revealed the most employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in the Housekeeping Department.

3.1.9. On the employable skills in the hotel industry, as perceived by the respondents in the Housekeeping Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Hospitality Operations Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

Table 9 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in the Housekeeping Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Hospitality Operations Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

SKILLS	1	2	3	4	N	WM	DV	R
A. Hospitality Operations								
1. Lodging Administration	0	1	7	12	20	3.55	GI	6
2. Restaurant Operational Management	0	1	8	11	20	3.50	GI	7
3. Food and Beverage Management	0	1	5	14	20	3.65	GI	3.5
4. Hospitality Facility Planning and Development	0	0	3	17	20	3.85	GI	1
5. Hospitality Finance and Accounting	0	1	6	13	20	3.60	GI	5
6. Marketing in Hospitality Industry	0	0	7	13	20	3.65	GI	3.5
7. Front Office Operational Ability	0	2	2	16	20	3.70	GI	2
Composite Mean						3.64	GI	

Table 9 shows that the most employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in Hospitality Operations were culled a composite mean of 3.64 with an interpretation as greatly important. Hospitality Facility Planning and Development has garnered a weighted mean of 3.85 with an interpretation as greatly important while Marketing in Hospitality Industry and Food and Beverage Management were captured a weighted mean of 3.65 with an interpretation as greatly important. The finding shows that if you were in the Housekeeping Department, the staff tasks in the various jobs were necessary for efficient and quality housekeeping and must see to it that such tasks were properly distributed. If there were plenty of guests to be served or the area to be maintained were quite large as in the case of big hotels, a rigid division of labor and specialization may be necessary this means that one position shall concentrate on a specific type of work.

3.1.10. On the employable skills in the hotel industry, as perceived by the respondents in the Housekeeping Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Human Resource Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

Table 10 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in the Housekeeping Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Human Resource Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

SKILLS	1	2	3	4	N	WM	DV	R
B. Human Resource Skills								
1. Leadership skills	0	0	2	18	20	3.90	GI	4
2. Communication skills	0	0	1	19	20	3.95	GI	1.5
3. Cooperative team building	0	0	2	18	20	3.90	GI	4
4. Negotiating skills	0	1	4	15	20	3.70	GI	8
5. Harmonious guest relations	0	0	2	18	20	3.90	GI	4
6. Handling Difficult People	0	0	1	19	20	3.95	GI	1.5
7. Employee Relations	0	0	3	17	20	3.85	GI	6.5
8. Public Relations skills	0	0	3	17	20	3.85	GI	6.5
Composite Mean						3.88	GI	

Table 10 shows that the most employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondent's Human Resource skills was generated a composite mean of 3.88 with an interpretation as greatly important. Communication skills and Handling difficult people have garnered a weighted mean of 3.95 respectively with an interpretation as greatly important; Leadership skills, Cooperative skills and handling difficult people were captured a weighted mean of 3.90 with an interpretation of greatly important. The finding shows that good management starts with proper communication. When a housekeeping supervisor has established his direction through his goals, plan, and operational procedures, he is better equipped to supervise the operation efficiently. But he must consistently and effectively lead, direct and monitor the implementation of the standard operating procedures to be able to generate the expected result's and to avoid guest complain and take corrective action or adopt some remedial measures to bridge any performance gap in handling difficult people.

3.1.11. *On the employable skills in the hotel industry, as perceived by the respondents in the Housekeeping Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Personal Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.*

Table 11 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in the Housekeeping Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Personal Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

SKILLS	1	2	3	4	N	WM	DV	R
C. Personal Skills								
1. Critical thinking ability	0	0	1	19	20	3.95	GI	1.5
2. Problem solving and identification	0	0	2	18	20	3.90	GI	3
3. Decision making skills	0	1	1	18	20	3.85	GI	4
4. Computer application	1	1	6	12	20	3.45	GI	8
5. Multilingual skills/need of second language	0	1	8	11	20	3.50	GI	7
6. Research skills	0	0	5	15	20	3.75	GI	6
7. Professionalism	0	1	2	17	20	3.80	GI	5
8. Hands – on – experience	0	0	1	19	20	3.95	GI	1.5
Composite Mean						3.77	GI	

Table 11 shows that the most employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in Personal skills were generated a composite mean of 3.77 with an interpretation as greatly important. Critical thinking ability and Hands – on – experience were reached 3.95 respectively, an interpretation as greatly important; Problem-solving and identification were reached to 3.95 with an interpretation as greatly important. The finding shows that it was the responsibility of the housekeeping supervisors to see to it that all housekeeping operations should meet productivity standards based on a given productivity ratio. One of the most important purposes of the housekeeping department was guest satisfaction is its primary objective.

3.1.12 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in the Housekeeping Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Conceptual Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

Table 12. On the employable skills in the hotel industry, as perceived by the respondents in the Housekeeping Department, the researcher wanted to find out the Conceptual Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

SKILLS	1	2	3	4	N	WM	DV	R
D. Conceptual Skills								
1. Organizational Structure and policies	0	0	7	13	20	3.65	GI	5
2. Hospitality law and regulations	0	0	6	14	20	3.70	GI	3
3. Principles of marketing	0	2	4	14	20	3.60	GI	6
4. Finance and Accounting	0	2	6	12	20	3.50	GI	7
5. Human Resource Management	0	2	2	16	20	3.70	GI	3
6. Interrelationships	0	1	3	16	20	3.75	GI	2
7. Strategic Planning	0	1	2	17	20	3.80	GI	1
Composite Mean						3.67	GI	

Table 12 shows that the most employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in Housekeeping Department under Conceptual Skills was Strategic planning with an average 3.80 and was greatly important and the composite mean of 3.67%. The finding shows that since the beginning, it has always been understood that the primary function of the housekeeping department is the cleaning of guestrooms and public areas purely maintenance work. To sustain an operation that will be able to deliver and at times even surpass guests expectations, a framework must be developed as a guidepost for improvement to constitutes the objectives of the department that everyone from the top to the least of the rank and file should work towards the department goal.

On table 13 to table 16 revealed the most employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in Three Departments.

3.1.13 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in three departments, the researcher wanted to find out the Hospitality Operations Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

Table 13 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in three departments, the researcher wanted to find out the Hospitality Operations Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

SKILLS	1	2	3	4	N	WM	DV	R
A. Hospitality Operations								
1. Lodging Administration	0	7	21	32	60	3.42	GI	7
2. Restaurant Operational Management	0	2	22	36	60	3.57	GI	4
3. Food and Beverage Management	0	4	16	40	60	3.60	GI	3
4. Hospitality Facility Planning and Development	0	3	16	41	60	3.63	GI	2
5. Hospitality Finance and Accounting	0	6	22	32	60	3.43	GI	6
6. Marketing in Hospitality Industry	0	4	21	35	60	3.52	GI	5
7. Front Office Operational Ability	0	4	13	43	60	3.65	GI	1
Composite Mean						3.55	GI	

Table 13 reveals that the most employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in three departments in the context of Hospitality Operation were garnered a composite mean of 3.55 with an interpretation as greatly important. Front Office Operational Ability Skills was reached to the weighted mean of 3.65 with an interpretation as greatly important; Hospitality Facility Planning and Development was garnered a weighted mean of 3.61 with the interpretation as greatly important; While Food and Beverage Management was obtained a weighted mean of 3.60 with the interpretation as greatly important. The finding shows that each department in the enterprise was expected to carry out its own specialized functions. The important part of the whole operation and must coordinate its activities with other department was the front office. Front office department was the heart of the hotel operation because this department has special responsibilities that create a more direct association with and it has a close working relationship such as engineering, Food and beverage, housekeeping, laundry, purchasing and among other departments of the hotel.

3.1.14 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in three departments, the researcher wanted to find out the Human Resource Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

Table 14 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in three departments, the researcher wanted to find out the Human Resource Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

SKILLS	1	2	3	4	N	WM	DV	R
B. Human Resource Skills								
1. Leadership skills	0	0	12	48	60	3.80	GI	2
2. Communication skills	0	1	10	49	60	3.80	GI	2
3. Cooperative team building	0	2	8	50	60	3.80	GI	2
4. Negotiating skills	0	3	17	40	60	3.62	GI	7
5. Harmonious guest relations	0	3	11	46	60	3.72	GI	5
6. Handling difficult people	0	2	10	48	60	3.77	GI	4
7. Employee Relations	0	4	16	40	60	3.60	GI	8
8. Public Relations Skills	0	3	14	43	60	3.67	GI	6
Composite Mean						3.72	GI	

Table 14 reveals that the most employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in three Departments in the context of Human Resource skills was culled of a composite mean of 3.72 with an interpretation as greatly important. Leadership skills, Communication skills, and Cooperative team building were garnered a 3.80 with an interpretation as greatly important; while handling difficult people was garnered a weighted mean of 3.77 with an interpretation as greatly important. The finding shows that a good supervisor starts with proper training and self-disciplined. Leadership, by example, is a key principle advocated by every responsible supervisor. As much as possible, he does not give employees a negative impression of his character, values, and work ethic. Whatever employees see and observed in him will be followed, imitated, and even magnified. A key

ingredient to order and productivity were communication and cooperative team building among employees to motivate at all levels through his words of encouragement and gentle demeanor.

3.1.15 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in three departments, the researcher wanted to find out the Personal Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

Table 15 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in three departments, the researcher wanted to find out the Personal Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

SKILLS	1	2	3	4	N	WM	DV	R
C. Personal Skills								
1. Critical thinking ability	0	2	7	51	60	3.82	GI	1.5
2. Problem solving and identification	0	2	8	50	60	3.80	GI	3
3. Decision making skills	0	3	10	47	60	3.73	GI	4
4. Computer application	1	5	29	25	60	3.30	GI	7
5. Multilingual skills/ need of second language	0	9	27	24	60	3.25	GI	8
6. Research skills	0	6	23	31	60	3.42	GI	6
7. Professionalism	0	3	14	43	60	3.67	GI	5
8. Hands – on – experience	0	2	7	51	60	3.82	GI	1.5
Composite Mean						3.60	GI	

Table 15 shows that the most employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in the Housekeeping Department in the context of Personal skills were obtained a composite mean of 3.60 with an interpretation as greatly important. Critical thinking ability and Hands – on - experience were reached to the weighted mean of 3.82 with an interpretation as greatly important while Problem Solving and Identification were garnered a weighted mean of 3.80 with an interpretation as greatly important. The finding shows that personals skills are a significant agent of the organization, both results-oriented and process oriented to value not only achievements but also a lesson learned in every transaction and experience in the operations.

3.1.16 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in three departments, the researcher wanted to find out the Conceptual Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

Table 16 On the employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in three departments, the researcher wanted to find out the Conceptual Skills of respondents working in the hospitality industry.

SKILLS	1	2	3	4	N	WM	DV	R
D. Conceptual Skills								
1. Organizational structure and policies	0	3	25	32	60	3.48	GI	4
2. Hospitality law and regulations	0	6	18	36	60	3.50	GI	3
3. Principles of marketing	0	7	26	27	60	3.33	GI	6
4. Finance and Accounting	0	8	26	26	60	3.30	GI	7
5. Human Resource Management	0	5	22	33	60	3.47	GI	5
6. Interrelationships	0	3	21	36	60	3.55	GI	2
7. Strategic Planning	0	3	18	39	60	3.60	GI	1
Composite Mean						3.46	GI	

Table 16 shows that the most employable skills in the hotel industry as perceived by the respondents in three departments in the context of Conceptual skills were garnered a composite mean of 3.46 with an interpretation as greatly important. Strategic planning was garnered a weighted mean of 3.60 with an interpretation as greatly

important; Interrelationships has obtained a weighted mean of 3.55 with an interpretation as greatly important while Hospitality Laws and Regulation was garnered a weighted mean of 3.50 with an interpretation as greatly important. The finding shows that the intent of the supervisor should be the first consideration for any employee who is evaluating a strategic decision. It is very important to make sure that the employee should not clash or conflict with each other's command responsibility, determine levels of authority, and guide the lines of communication.

4. Conclusion

In the context of the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that the most employable skills as perceived by hotel supervisors in three departments (Housekeeping, Front Office and Food and Beverage) were Front Office Operational Ability, Leadership skills, Communication skills, Cooperative team building, Critical thinking ability, Hands-on experience, and Strategic planning were the seven employable skills possessing a most or greatly important need for hotel supervisors. Therefore, it can be implied that these skills offered in high need for curriculum enhancement. However, Restaurant Operational Management, Handling difficult people, Problem-solving and identification and interrelationship possess moderately important than their ability to perform the skills. Therefore, faculty in the college should investigate ways of enhancing while lodging administration, Negotiating skills, Computer Application and Finance and Accounting. Interestingly all four of the lowest rated employable skills in the hospitality industry are cornerstones taught, and it should still be retained because of its important ratings by the hotel supervisors.

5. Recommendations

The researcher recommended that this study

1. The HEIs must create awareness to graduates on the needs and expectations of the globalized job market. The implication of these findings for graduates and training providers are to provide opportunities for graduates to develop and use a range of skills to remain more competitive in the labor market. This can be done through industry attachment during their study or by negotiated job enlargement and enrichment with industry.
2. Should share with the faculty as a means to improve future graduate's competencies at performing the employable skills. This suggests that skills developments opportunities during their study in university are a key issue that needs to be addressed
3. Should be shared with industry professionals to close the gap between employers and educators, the implementation of the syllabus structure must involve both parties. Employers can be involved in providing input for the design and evaluation of particular subjects in the curriculum and the quality of graduates is increasingly becoming an important issue to both the higher learning institutions where graduates obtain their qualification to build and sustain rapport and keep communication lines open and supervisors represented the organization where provided feedback concerning graduates competencies were analyzed according to what they believed was greatly important in the way of employable ability skills to the workplace.
4. Future research should consist of more focused studies for each academic department represented. This would bring more clarity to each department as to the exact skill(s) in need and thus would allow for adequate enhancements to be made to all curricula. In addition, the researcher recommends in the future making a training module based on the Human Resource Skills (i.e., leadership Skills, communication skills, and cooperative team building skills, handling difficult people and public relations skills.

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